

A complete proof of convergence for a nearest-prime recurrence to the golden ratio

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Abstract

We prove unconditionally that for any positive integers a_1, a_2 , the sequence defined by

$$a_n = \text{the prime nearest to } a_{n-1} + a_{n-2} \quad (n \geq 3),$$

with ties broken by taking the smaller prime, satisfies

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{a_n}{a_{n-1}} = \varphi := \frac{1 + \sqrt{5}}{2}.$$

The proof uses the Baker–Harman–Pintz prime gap theorem (unconditional) and elementary real analysis.

1 Notation

For $n \geq 3$, set

$$s_n = a_{n-1} + a_{n-2}, \quad e_n = a_n - s_n.$$

Thus $|e_n|$ is the distance from s_n to the nearest prime.

2 Prime gap estimate

Theorem 1 (Baker, Harman, Pintz (2001)). *There exist constants $C_0 > 0$ and $x_0 \geq 1$ such that for all integers $x \geq x_0$,*

$$\text{dist}(x, \text{primes}) \leq C_0 x^\theta, \quad \theta = 0.525.$$

Consequently, for all n with $s_n \geq x_0$,

$$|e_n| \leq C_0 s_n^\theta. \tag{1}$$

3 Lemma 1: $s_n \rightarrow \infty$

Lemma 1. For any initial positive integers a_1, a_2 , we have $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} s_n = \infty$.

Proof. Let $M = \max(a_{n-1}, a_{n-2})$ and $m = \min(a_{n-1}, a_{n-2})$. Then $s_n = M + m$. Since M itself is a prime (all terms are primes by construction), it is a candidate prime at distance m from s_n . Any prime smaller than M is at distance at least $m + 1$ from s_n (the next lower prime is at most $M - 2$, giving distance $s_n - (M - 2) = m + 2 > m$). Hence the nearest prime to s_n cannot be smaller than M . Therefore

$$a_n \geq M = \max(a_{n-1}, a_{n-2}).$$

Thus the running maximum is nondecreasing.

Now assume, for contradiction, that the sequence is bounded. Since the running maximum is nondecreasing and bounded, it must eventually become constant. Let p be this eventual constant maximum. From some index onward, all terms are $\leq p$ and the maximum is exactly p . By the property above, whenever a term equals p , the next term satisfies $a_{n+1} \geq \max(a_n, a_{n-1}) \geq p$. Because the maximum cannot exceed p , we must have $a_{n+1} = p$. Consequently, after the first occurrence of p , the following term is also p , giving two consecutive terms equal to p .

Suppose then that for some n we have $a_n = a_{n+1} = p$. Then $s_{n+2} = 2p$. By Bertrand's postulate, there exists a prime q with $p < q < 2p$. The distance from $2p$ to this prime q is $2p - q < p$, while the distance to p is p . Hence the nearest prime to $2p$ is strictly greater than p , contradicting the assumption that p is the maximum. Therefore the sequence cannot be bounded; it is unbounded.

Since the sequence is unbounded, $a_n \rightarrow \infty$. Consequently $s_n = a_{n-1} + a_{n-2} \rightarrow \infty$.

4 Lemma 2: Relative error tends to zero

By Lemma 1, $s_n \rightarrow \infty$, hence there exists N_0 such that for all $n \geq N_0$, $s_n \geq x_0$. From (1) we obtain

$$\frac{|e_n|}{s_n} \leq C_0 s_n^{\theta-1} \rightarrow 0, \quad \text{since } \theta - 1 < 0.$$

Thus for any $\varepsilon > 0$, eventually

$$(1 - \varepsilon)s_n \leq a_n \leq (1 + \varepsilon)s_n. \tag{2}$$

5 Lemma 3: Convergence of the ratio

Define $r_n = a_n/a_{n-1}$ for $n \geq 2$. From (2), for large n ,

$$(1 - \varepsilon) \left(1 + \frac{1}{r_{n-1}}\right) \leq r_n \leq (1 + \varepsilon) \left(1 + \frac{1}{r_{n-1}}\right). \tag{3}$$

We first show that r_n is eventually bounded away from 0 and ∞ . Choose $\varepsilon < 1/2$. Then for sufficiently large n ,

$$r_n \geq (1 - \varepsilon) \left(1 + \frac{1}{r_{n-1}}\right) \geq 1 - \varepsilon > 0.$$

Thus the ratios have a positive lower bound. For an upper bound, note that from the right inequality in (3) and the fact that r_{n-1} is bounded below by a positive constant, we obtain an eventual upper bound as well (for example, if $r_{n-1} \geq c > 0$, then $r_n \leq (1+\varepsilon)(1+1/c)$). Hence there exist constants $0 < L \leq U < \infty$ such that

$$L = \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} r_n, \quad U = \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} r_n.$$

Fix an arbitrary $\varepsilon > 0$. For all sufficiently large n , (3) holds. Taking \liminf in the left inequality and \limsup in the right inequality gives

$$L \geq (1 - \varepsilon) \left(1 + \frac{1}{U}\right), \quad U \leq (1 + \varepsilon) \left(1 + \frac{1}{L}\right).$$

Since ε is arbitrary, letting $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+$ yields

$$L \geq 1 + \frac{1}{U}, \quad U \leq 1 + \frac{1}{L}. \quad (4)$$

From (4), $L \geq 1+1/U$ implies $LU \geq U+1$. Similarly, $U \leq 1+1/L$ implies $LU \leq L+1$. Hence $U+1 \leq L+1$, so $U \leq L$. Since always $L \leq U$, we obtain $L = U$. Thus $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} r_n$ exists; denote it by r . Then (4) becomes

$$r = 1 + \frac{1}{r},$$

hence $r^2 - r - 1 = 0$, and the positive solution is $r = \varphi$.

6 Lemma 4: Exponential growth

Since $\log r_k \rightarrow \log \varphi$, Cesàro's theorem gives

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=2}^n \log r_k = \log \varphi.$$

But $\sum_{k=2}^n \log r_k = \log a_n - \log a_1$. Therefore

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\log a_n}{n} = \log \varphi,$$

so $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} a_n^{1/n} = \varphi$.

7 Conclusion

We have proved unconditionally that for any positive integers a_1, a_2 ,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{a_n}{a_{n-1}} = \varphi.$$

The proof uses the Baker–Harman–Pintz theorem and elementary real analysis.

References

- [1] R. C. Baker, G. Harman, and J. Pintz, *The difference between consecutive primes, II*, Proc. London Math. Soc. (3) 83 (2001), no. 3, 532–562.

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